

Synthesis of Substituted Arylhydrazones of 4-Aryl-4H-1,2,4-Triazolyl-3-Thioacetic Acid Hydrazides

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Some 4-Aryl-4H-1, 2, 4-triazolyl-3-thioacetic acid hydrazides and their substituted arylhydrazones were prepared and screened for antibacterial, antifungal and antifungal activities. These compounds showed weak antimicrobial activity.

ISONICOTINIC acid hydrazide (INH) and its derivatives are well known for their antitubercular activity¹. Several 4H-1,2,4-triazole derivatives are also known to possess antimicrobial activity^{2,3}. Accordingly, earlier we had prepared several 4-aryl-4H-triazolyl-3-thioacetic acids which had shown a weak antifungal activity⁴. It was also observed that some of the schiff bases prepared in this laboratory by condensing amines with halosalicylaldehydes had shown antimicrobial activity⁵. Hence as a part of our programme for finding potential antibacterial and antifungal agents, substituted arylhydrazones of 4-aryl-4H-1, 2, 4-triazolyl-3-thioacetic acid hydrazides were synthesised by the following sequence of reactions and they are reported here; but on screening none of them showed any significant expected activity at 50 mcg/ml level.

1. 4-Arylthiosemicarbazides were cyclised with ethylformate in presence of sodium methoxide to get 3-mercapto-4-aryl-4H-1,2,4-triazoles(I).

2. The mercapto triazoles(I) were reacted with ethylchloroacetate to give 3-thioacetic acid esters, which were further reacted with hydrazine hydrate to 4-aryl-4H, 1, 2, 4-triazolyl-3-thioacetic acid hydrazides(II).

3. The hydrazides(II) were reacted with substituted benzaldehydes to get the title compounds.

Experimental

Preparation of 4-Aryl-3-mercapto-4H-1, 2, 4-triazoles :

Prepared by the method as described in our communication reported earlier⁴.

Preparation of 4-Aryl-4H-1,2,4-triazolyl-3-thioacetic acid hydrazides :

Prepared by the method described earlier⁷. 4-Aryl-3-mercapto-4H-1, 2, 4-triazoles (1 mol) in acetone were refluxed with ethylchloroacetate

(2 mol) in presence of anhydrous sodium carbonate (4 mol) for 6 hours. The reaction mixture was cooled and filtered. The solvent and unreacted ethylchloroacetate were removed under reduced pressure to get crude 4-aryl-4H-1, 2, 4-triazolyl-3-thioacetic acid esters. These esters (1 mol) were further reacted with hydrazine hydrate (2 mol : 94-96%) in alcohol at room temperature to get clear solution. Within half an hour most of the hydrazides crystallised out. They were recrystallised from hot alcohol (50-55% yield).

Preparation of substituted Arylhydrazones of 4-aryl-4H-1,2,4-triazolyl-3-thioacetic acid hydrazides :

Prepared by the method described earlier⁸. 4-Aryl-4H-1,2,4-triazolyl-3-thioacetic acid hydrazides (1 mol) in alcohol were added to substituted benzaldehydes (1 mol) in alcohol in presence of acetic acid at 60-70°. On cooling the reaction mixture, the title compounds were obtained as crystalline solids. They were recrystallised from hot alcohol.

The compounds are listed in Tables 1-6.

TABLE I
4-ARYL-4H-1, 2, 4-TRIAZOLYL-3-THIOACETIC ACID HYDRAZIDES

Sl. No.	R	M. P. °C*	Molecular Formula	Nitrogen % Found	Nitrogen % Calc.
1.	3-CH ₃	159-61	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂ S	26.5	26.6
2.	4-CH ₃	144-46	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂ S	27.0	26.6
3.	2-OCH ₃	168-65	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₃ S	25.6	25.0
4.	3-OCH ₃	170-72	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₃ S	24.9	25.0
5.	4-OCH ₃	173-76	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₃ S	25.7	25.0
6.	2-Cl	168	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	24.9	24.6
7.	3-Cl	188-91	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	24.8	24.6
8.	4-Cl	164-67	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	24.0	24.6
9.	4-Br	170-72	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ BrN ₃ O ₂ S	21.4	21.3
10.	4-I	201-03	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ I ₂ N ₃ O ₂ S	18.9	18.3
11.	3-CF ₃	157-59	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ F ₃ N ₃ O ₂ S	21.9	22.5
12.	2, 4-(CH ₃) ₂	167-70	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂ S	26.5	26.2
13.	2-CH ₃ -4-Cl	144-47	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	24.0	23.5
14.	2-CH ₃ -5-Cl	135-37	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	22.9	23.5

* All the melting points are uncorrected.

TABLE 2

2-HYDROXYPHENYLHYDRAZONES OF 4-ARYL-4H-1, 2, 4-TRIAZOLYL-3-THIOACETIC ACID HYDRAZIDES

Sl. No.	R	M. P. °C*	Molecular Formula	Nitrogen %	
				Found	Calc.
1.	3-CH ₃	140-43	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	18.8	19.0
2.	4-CH ₃	175-77	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	18.4	19.0
3.	2-OCH ₃	286-40	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	18.4	18.2
4.	3-OCH ₃	163-65	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	17.4	18.2
5.	4-OCH ₃	207-12	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	17.7	18.2
6.	2-Cl	201-05	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	18.2	18.0
7.	3-Cl	161-63	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	18.8	18.0
8.	4-Cl	202-04	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	18.2	18.0
9.	4-Br	224-26	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ BrN ₃ O ₂ S	15.8	16.2
10.	4-I	247-49	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ IN ₃ O ₂ S	15.1	14.6
11.	3-CF ₃	176-80	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ F ₃ N ₃ O ₂ S	16.8	16.8
12.	2, 4-(CH ₃) ₂	168-70	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂ S	18.8	18.3
13.	2-CH ₃ -4-Cl	180-85	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	17.3	17.4
14.	2-CH ₃ -5-Cl	196-99	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	17.9	17.4

* All the melting points are uncorrected.

TABLE 3

3-HYDROXYPHENYLHYDRAZONES OF 4-ARYL-4H-1, 2, 4-TRIAZOLYL-3-THIOACETIC ACID HYDRAZIDES

Sl. No.	R	M. P. °C*	Molecular Formula	Nitrogen %	
				Found	Calc.
**1.	H	243-45	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂ S	19.4	19.8
**2.	2-CH ₃	229-31	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	19.0	19.0
3.	3-CH ₃	230-32	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	18.9	19.0
4.	4-CH ₃	220-22	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	19.5	19.0
5.	2-OCH ₃	229-32	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	18.6	18.2
6.	3-OCH ₃	214-16	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	18.0	18.2
7.	4-OCH ₃	204-07	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	18.6	18.2
8.	2-Cl	240-41	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	18.9	18.0
9.	3-Cl	230-32	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	17.9	18.0
10.	4-Cl	240-43	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	18.2	18.0
11.	4-Br	249-51	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ BrN ₃ O ₂ S	15.8	16.2
12.	4-I	242-44	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ IN ₃ O ₂ S	15.0	14.6
13.	3-CF ₃	197-99	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ F ₃ N ₃ O ₂ S	16.5	16.8
14.	2, 4-(CH ₃) ₂	210-13	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂ S	19.0	18.3
15.	2-CH ₃ -4-Cl	220-23	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	17.0	17.4
16.	2-CH ₃ -5-Cl	239-41	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	17.2	17.4

* All the melting points are uncorrected.¹

** V. Zotta, *Ann Tataru, Farmacia*, 1975, 23(4), 193-6.

TABLE 4

4-HYDROXYPHENYLHYDRAZONES OF 4-ARYL-4H-1, 2, 4-TRIAZOLYL-3-THIOACETIC ACID HYDRAZIDES

Sl. No.	R	M. P. °C*	Molecular Formula	Nitrogen %	
				Found	Calc.
**1.	H	252-54	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂ S	19.4	19.8
**2.	2-CH ₃	168-70	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	18.7	19.0
3.	3-CH ₃	190-92	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	18.7	19.0
4.	4-CH ₃	256-59	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	19.1	19.0
5.	2-OCH ₃	248-50	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	17.7	18.2
6.	3-OCH ₃	186-87	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	17.8	18.2
7.	4-OCH ₃	212-14	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	17.8	18.2
8.	2-Cl	160	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	17.2	18.0
9.	3-Cl	208-11	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	18.5	18.0
10.	4-Cl	261-61	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	18.7	18.0
11.	4-Br	265-66	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ BrN ₃ O ₂ S	15.7	16.2
12.	4-I	265-67	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ IN ₃ O ₂ S	14.7	14.6
13.	3-CF ₃ ¹	173-75	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ F ₃ N ₃ O ₂ S	16.5	16.8
14.	2, 4-(CH ₃) ₂	236-38	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂ S	18.1	18.3
15.	2-CH ₃ -4-Cl	201-05	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	17.1	17.4
16.	2-CH ₃ -5-Cl	215-18	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	17.9	17.4

* All the melting points are uncorrected.

** V. Zotta, *Ann Tataru, Farmacia*, 1975, 23(4), 193-6.

TABLE 5

2-HYDROXY-5-CHLOROPHENYLHYDRAZONES OF 4-ARYL-4H-1, 2, 4-TRIAZOLYL-3-THIOACETIC ACID HYDRAZIDES

Sl. No.	R	M. P. °C*	Molecular Formula	Nitrogen %	
				Found	Calc.
1.	H	218-20	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	18.5	18.0
2.	2-CH ₃	194-96	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	17.6	17.4
3.	3-CH ₃	183-85	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	17.5	17.4
4.	4-CH ₃	220-22	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	18.1	17.4
5.	2-OCH ₃	235-87	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	17.0	16.7
6.	3-OCH ₃	248-49	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	17.1	16.7
7.	4-OCH ₃	150-54	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	17.4	16.7
8.	2-Cl	248-50	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₂ S	17.2	16.5
9.	3-Cl	193-95	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₂ S	17.1	16.5
10.	4-Cl	219-22	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₂ S	17.1	16.5
11.	4-Br	235-99	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ BrClN ₃ O ₂ S	15.1	15.0
12.	4-I	240	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ ClIN ₃ O ₂ S	15.3	15.0
13.	3-CF ₃	196-98	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ ClF ₃ N ₃ O ₂ S	15.8	15.5
14.	2, 4-(CH ₃) ₂	200-01	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	17.1	16.8
15.	2-CH ₃ -4-Cl	215-17	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₂ S	16.5	16.0
16.	2-CH ₃ -5-Cl	200-02	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₂ S	16.4	16.0

* All the melting points are uncorrected.

TABLE 6

2-HYDROXY-5-BROMOPHENYLHYDRAZONES OF 4-ARYL-4H-1, 2, 4-TRIAZOLYL-3-THIOACETIC ACID HYDRAZIDES

Sl. No.	R	M. P. °C*	Molecular Formula	Nitrogen %	
				Found	Calc.
1.	H	198-99	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ BrN ₃ O ₂ S	16.4	16.0
2.	2-CH ₃	200-02	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ BrN ₃ O ₂ S	15.6	15.7
3.	3-CH ₃	199-95	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ BrN ₃ O ₂ S	16.2	15.7
4.	4-CH ₃	200-11	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ BrN ₃ O ₂ S	15.9	15.7
5.	2-OCH ₃	225-27	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ BrN ₃ O ₂ S	15.0	15.1
6.	3-OCH ₃	240-45	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ BrN ₃ O ₂ S	15.2	15.1
7.	4-OCH ₃	165-66	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ BrN ₃ O ₂ S	15.4	15.1
8.	2-Cl	245	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ BrClN ₃ O ₂ S	15.2	15.0
9.	3-Cl	195-98	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ BrClN ₃ O ₂ S	15.0	15.0
10.	4-Cl	226-29	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ BrClN ₃ O ₂ S	15.6	15.0
11.	4-Br	240-44	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ Br ₂ N ₃ O ₂ S	14.2	13.5
12.	4-I	252-54	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ BrIN ₃ O ₂ S	13.0	12.5
13.	3-CF ₃	208-10	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ BrF ₃ N ₃ O ₂ S	13.6	14.1
14.	2, 4-(CH ₃) ₂	202-05	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ BrN ₃ O ₂ S	15.8	15.2
15.	2-CH ₃ -4-Cl	212-15	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ BrClN ₃ O ₂ S	14.1	14.5
16.	2-CH ₃ -5-Cl	222-24	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ BrClN ₃ O ₂ S	14.6	14.5

* All the melting points are uncorrected.

Biological data

The *in vitro* antibacterial, antituberculous and antifungal activities were studied by the serial dilution method⁶. As the solutions of the compounds in dimethylformamide (DMF) and dilutions were made such that in no instance there was more than 1% DMF in the medium under study. It was confirmed that DMF at such concentrations had no inhibitory effect on the organisms under test. For antibacterial screening, the inoculated broth tubes were incubated at 37° for 24 hours and the dilution inhibiting the growth was noted. For antifungal screening, the inoculated broth tubes were inoculated at 27° and the state of growth was observed for 96 hours and the dilution showing no visible growth was noted. Antituberculous tests were carried out in Lowenstein-

Jenson media. Results were recorded after three weeks incubation at 37° when tested at 50 mcg/ml concentration. These derivatives showed no inhibitory properties against the organisms.

(I) R=H; 2-, 3-, 4-CH₃; OCH₃ and Cl; 4-Br and I; 3-CF₃; 2, 4-(CH₃)₂; 2-CH₃-4-Cl; 2-CH₃-5-Cl

(II) R₁=2-, 3-, 4-OH; R₂=H

(III) R₁=2-OH; R₂=5-Cl; 5-Br.

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